

HEMATOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL FEATURE ASSOCIATED TO CHILDREN WITH INTESTINAL HELMINTHS IN DISTRICT KOHAT

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Abstract

Intestinal helminth infections remain a significant public health issue, particularly in developing regions. This study investigates the hematological and biochemical profiles of children diagnosed with intestinal helminthiasis in District Kohat, Pakistan. Blood samples were taken from 150 intestinal helminth-infected children, as well as 50 from the control group were taken from children of children up to 12 years. Frequency counts, percentages, averages, standard deviations, and correlations analyzed the data. The stool test revealed that the cyst no and *Enterobius vermicularis* were found more prevalent in the stool samples of the children. Results of complete blood count (CBC) of 150 confirmed intestinal helminths infection were randomly choosing and compared with CBC reports of non-infected individuals. Albumin to globulin ratio (1.27 ± 0.7), Red Blood Cell (RBC) ($4.49 \pm 0.56 \times 10^6 / \mu\text{L}$), Hemoglobin (HB) ($11.64 \pm 1.23 \text{ g/dL}$), Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) ($75.4 \pm 3.34 \text{ fL}$) and Neutrophils ($57.56 \pm 8.43 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$) were less than mean values of normal. Median values for Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) of both patients and control was almost same and Hematocrit (HCT) ($42.16 \pm 2.44\%$), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH) ($75.4 \pm 3.34 \text{ pg}$), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) ($35.03 \pm 3.61 \text{ g/dL}$), Platelets (PLT) ($291.07 \pm 48.7 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$), Lymphocytes ($31.53 \pm 9.22 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$), Monocytes ($7.31 \pm 3.87 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$) and Eosinophils ($5.09 \pm 1.23 \times 10^3 / \mu\text{L}$) was higher than normal mean values The study aimed to assay some immunological markers and nutritional deficiency in children infected with single or multiple helminths resident in Districts Kohat.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most prevalent infectious diseases, The effects of intestinal parasite infections roughly 3.5 billion people annually and result in over 450 million health issues, such as diarrhea, abdominal pain, malnourishment, frailty as well as impaired development and growth. Up to 2010, there were 45,927 recorded deaths and 23.2 million cases of

foodborne parasite illness (not including enteric protozoa), according to the WHO. It was revealed that foodborne enteric protozoa were responsible for an extra 67.2 million cases of sickness. Severe infections led to neurological and mental disorders as well as significant disability. Children are particularly vulnerable to these diseases, and

reinfection is common among them (Faustian *et al.*, 2022).

Over 267 million children in preschool and over 568 million children in school reside in epidemic areas, accounting for around 24% of the world's population affected with intestinal parasite infections (WHO, 2019). In 2016, the World Health Organization (WHO) stated, up to 55.3% of children and up to 36% of the global population are thought to be affected by parasitoids. Prophylactic administration of antiparasitic drugs against soil-transmitted helminthes is recommended by the WHO for at-risk groups in places where helminthes infections are highly prevalent (more than 20% annually or greater than 50% biannually). because it is costly and impractical to collect and test stool samples prior to treatment in many low-income contexts (Celestino *et al.*, 2021).

It is projected that 820 million roundworms, 460 million whipworms, and 440 million hookworms are impacted globally. (WHO, 2017). The environment and the host are both necessary for the helminth parasites' growth and survival. Transmission frequently happens when untreated human or animal waste is used as fertilizer and contaminates the soil. Because of untreated wastewater and poor sanitation, vegetables irrigated with tainted water and water with helminth eggs that have been embryonized may also serve as vehicles of transmission (Javanmard *et al.*, 2018). Mostly found in poor nations, intestinal parasite infections continue to be a serious public health issue that severely damages the socioeconomic standing of disadvantaged rural people (Swaroop *et al.*, 2014).

Over 2 billion people worldwide are afflicted with geohelminthic infections, and in two-thirds of African nations with high-risk locations, the prevalence is greater than 50% (Strunz *et al.*, 2016). At 807 to 1221 million cases worldwide, especially in East Asia and sub-Saharan Africa, *A. lumbricoides* remains one of the most common intestinal helminths. Furthermore, 604 to 795 million infections are caused by the whipworm (*T. trichiura*), whereas 576 to 740 million infections are caused by the hookworm (Saki *et al.*, 2017) According to WHO, around 2 billion people are infected with STHs, However, 1.1 billion people worldwide lack

access to better water sources, and 2.4 billion need access to better sanitary facilities. As a result, diarrheal diseases claim the lives of around 2 million individuals annually, with children under the age of five making up the majority. Developing nations are the most affected, with the most of these individuals living in rural or periurban areas, in poverty, and in poor health (Doni *et al.*, 2015).

As potential risk factors, demographic characteristics (ethnicity, urban/rural residence, mother's age, and gender), indicators of social advantage (home ownership, occupation, education, and TV/radio ownership), and daily life and housing-related characteristics (use of soap, cooking location, domestic animals, garbage disposal method, access to water, toilet type, and roof type) were all examined. The main risk factors for contracting STH infection are poor sanitation, low socioeconomic position, poor personal hygiene, and living in rural regions. Other risk factors for STH infection in preschoolers include a crowded home setting, an unclean playground, and poor personal hygiene on the part of the child and the mother or caregiver (Novianty *et al.*, 2018).

Intestinal parasite infections are frequently brought on by poor sanitation, inadequate hygiene, and an inability to obtain clean drinking water. The parasites can infect people of all ages who have inadequate access to clean water and sanitation, but children are particularly vulnerable. Poor physical, mental, and social health as well as subpar work performance and job loss were caused by parasite infections. These diseases are more common in areas with high levels of poverty. The size of the family, the child's bad health, and the parents' reading level are additional risk factors. The impoverished in less developed countries are more likely to experience recurrent illnesses and malnutrition, which can result in unfavorable morbidity that can persist for generations. Parasites can lead to iron deficiency anemia, stunted child growth, diarrheal diseases, cognitive impairment, malnutrition, protein depletion, vitamin deficiencies, or even surgical complications like intestinal blockage and increased susceptibility to other infections. According to certain research, parasitic infections can be lethal and have a substantial correlation with anemia,

AIDS, cancer, organic brain disease, and mental sickness (Arshad *et al.*, 2019).

The intricacy of intestinal helminth lifecycles varies widely. However, since some species' eggs can survive for years in the environment, environmental Open defecation resulting in intestinal helminth egg contamination frequently plays a major role in continuing transmission. A wide variety of fish and animals are also crucial in the spread of numerous intestinal helminths to people. In certain instances, eating contaminated meat or fish can directly spread the disease from animals to people (e.g. *Taenia solium*) (WHO, 2019). In other instances, animals release helminth eggs into the environment, where they might be consumed by people (as in the case of *Ascaris lumbricoides*), penetrate human skin (as in the case of hookworm), or infect gastropod intermediate hosts before being transmitted to humans (as in the case of *Schistosoma japonicum*) (Jourdan *et al.*, 2018).

Human serum albumin is the protein that is most commonly found in human blood plasma. With a normal concentration of 3.5–5 g/dl, it accounts for approximately 50–60% of total plasma protein in healthy adults. Comprising 585 amino acid residues, it is a globular protein with a molecular weight of roughly 66.5 kDa. At neutral pH, it possesses a negative charge and a half-life of about 21 days. An albumin molecule consists of 35 cysteine (Cys) residues, 34 of which stabilize the protein's secondary structure by forming 17 disulfide bonds (S-S). The single free redox-active thiol (–SH) found in the Cys residue at site 34, commonly referred to as Cys-34, is the primary source of redox-active thiols in plasma. (Garcia-Martinez *et al.*, 2013).

Both reduced and oxidized forms of albumin can be found in plasma, depending on Cys-34's condition. The main form of HSA is its reduced form, called human mercaptalbumin (HMA), which is present in 70–80% of young, healthy individuals. Depending on whether it is irreversible or reversible, its oxidized form is further divided into human non-mercaptalbumin 1 (HNA1) and human non-mercaptalbumin 2 (HNA2). Homocysteine, glutathione, and cysteine are examples of small molecule substances that contain thiols and can interact with HNA1, a common reversibly oxidized albumin. Because of this, it usually resides as mixed

disulfide compounds, which account for 20–30% of albumin in young, healthy individuals. Between 2 and 5% of the blood in young, healthy individuals contains HNA2, a highly oxidized version of albumin with a Cys-34 residue modified with sulfinic or sulfonic acid. Each of the three homologous domains I, II, and III—which make up the heart-shaped tertiary structure of albumin—has two subdomains (Oetzel *et al.*, 2007).

Mostly produced by hepatocytes (10–15 g/day), A single gene produces albumin, which is then delivered to the Golgi apparatus through the endoplasmic reticulum after the N terminal propeptide is removed. The rate of albumin synthesis is dependent on the nutritional status of each individual. However, additional variables also control the synthesis of HSA. For instance, growth hormone stimulation and hypoalbuminemia greatly increase the formation of HSA (27, 29); conversely, pro-inflammatory cytokines [including interleukin 6 (IL 6) and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF α)] prevent its synthesis (Wu *et al.*, 2023).

It was originally believed that albumin's advantages relied on its capacity to preserve the equilibrium of blood colloid osmotic pressure and guarantee communication between intracellular, extracellular, and tissue fluid because it accounts for roughly 70–80% of plasma's total osmotic pressure and serves as the main regulator of fluid distribution in the body cavity. Because of this, it was first used as a plasma expander in the 1950s and was frequently used to increase the volume of blood in circulation in patients who had suffered burns, shock, or blood loss. However, a thorough knowledge of HSA's biological role has revealed that albumin has a variety of biological impacts and that its non-colloid function is just as important as its colloidal function. The non-oncotic activities of albumin principally include antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, molecular transport, endothelium stabilization and immune modulation (Baldassarre *et al.*, 2021).

In response to inflammatory and infectious responses, the liver and plasma cells primarily produce and secrete globulin, a significant component of serum proteins. The two main constituents of globulin are inflammatory cytokines and antibodies (Ye *et al.*, 2020). Serum globulin, also

known as the gamma gap or protein gap, includes all non-albumin proteins, including globulin, fibrinogen, C-reactive protein, interleukins, leukotrienes, and other regulatory and prothrombotic proteins. It is frequently calculated as the difference between albumin and total protein. (Peng *et al.*, 2020).

Serum globulin levels can rise in diseases like infection, inflammation, and liver and connective tissue disorders, while they can fall in nephrotic syndrome and starvation because of reduced protein synthesis and loss through the kidney, respectively (Pai *et al.*, 2022).

Immunoglobulins and other globulin proteins are examples of serum globulins, which are essential for immunological function. The main globulin components implicated in inflammation and immunity are immunoglobulins. Elevated serum globulin levels are widely acknowledged as a trustworthy marker for determining the degree of persistent inflammation and signaling an immunological and/or inflammatory reaction (Du *et al.*, 2016).

Since mononuclear phagocytes synthesize and secrete serum globulins, which are primarily made up of inflammatory cytokines and antibodies, they are believed to be an accurate indicator of the level and intensity of immunity and inflammation. One of the main components of total serum proteins is serum

globulins. Thus, the rise in serum globulin concentrations is due to the accumulation of immunoglobulins and acute inflammatory proteins. According to Pearson correlation tests, globulin and WBC levels are positively correlated (Hsieh *et al.*, 2023).

Objectives

- To conduct a comparative analysis of hematological parameters between helminth-infected and non-infected individuals
- To evaluate the albumin and globulin level of blood serum of intestinal helminthes infected children patients up to 12 years.

Materials And Methods

Ethical Approval

This Study was performed in the laboratory of parasitology Department of Zoology KUST, Kohat, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. All the procedures were approved by Research Ethical Committee of KUST, Kohat

Study Area

This Study was conducted in the district Kohat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, from May 2024 to November 2024. Kohat geographically coordinates having Latitude: 33.58, Longitude: 71.44 and 33° 32' 13" North, 72° 25' 29" East (Figure 1).

Figure.1 Map of district Kohat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Sample Collection

Stool samples were collected in a plastic container using wooden sticks, mixed with distilled water or iodine, and then studied under a microscope to detect the presence of any parasite stage. 150 children who tested positive for various intestinal helminth infestations were included in this study, and 50 samples were taken as a control group from children who visited hospitals but tested negative for intestinal helminth infections. To assess the blood parameters (WBC, HB, MCHC, PLT, RBC, MCH, and MCV), blood samples were taken from the kids. Additionally, biochemical testing on the affected youngsters were conducted.

Hematological Analysis

Intravenous 1.5 ml blood samples from intestinal helminth patients were placed in 5 ml EDTA tubes using a sterile disposable syringe. To keep the blood samples uniform, the tubes were positioned on the rotor. In order to record the results of CP (platelets count, MHC, MCV, MCHC, RBC, Hb, PCV, RDW-CV, platelet distribution width, mean platelet volume) and DLC (neutrophils, lymphocytes, monocytes, eosinophils, basophils, NRBC per 100WBCs, immature granulocytes), the blood sample was fed into the probe of the TOSOH automated hematology analyzer (Nawaz et al., 2023). By enabling controlled sample volume, dried blood spots (DBS), an alternate technique for obtaining venous blood samples that may be used to evaluate blood biomarkers, were utilized to reduce contamination (Prado et al., 2015).

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure.2 (A), (B), (C) show CBC setup, where CBC test was conducted for hematological analysis.

Biochemical Analysis

Patients with intestinal helminths had a whole blood sample (2 ml) drawn intravenously into a 5-ml glass tube with a yellow cap. For fifteen to twenty minutes, the blood was left to coagulate. The tubes were spun

for five minutes at 3000 rpm once the blood had completely clotted (Thermo-scientific LABOFUGE 200, Sweden). The tubes were carefully removed after centrifugation, and serum was extracted. The serum was divided into clear test tubes marked with

the patient's ID when the gel formed over the blood clot. To ascertain the quantities of albumin and globulin protein, the samples were put in a TOSOH G11 HPLC Analyzer in Japan, and the result produced for the research variables was noted.

Furthermore, immunoglobulins were analyzed to evaluate immune reaction and susceptibility to a particular helminth antigen. (Nawaz *et al.*, 2023).

Figure.3 (A) Test tube having serum of blood for the checking of albumin and globulin level.

Figure.3(B). Automatic chemistry machine run for the test of albumin and globulin level in blood serum.

Stool Test

Patients with intestinal helminths had their stool samples taken in a plastic container. To determine whether any parasite stages were present, the sample was obtained using wooden sticks, diluted with iodine to form a homogenous mixture, and then inspected under a microscope. The interior architecture of parasites and cysts are stained by iodine solution, increasing the diagnostic potential (Awaad *et al.*, 2023).

(A)

(B)

Figure.4 (A) and (B) show microscopy examination for stool test.

Statistical Analysis

After being collected, An Excel spreadsheet was created using the data and statistical analysis was performed. Hematological parameters, stool test results, and biochemical parameters were examined using the statistical software SPSS version 25.0 and Graph Pad Prism version. The following formula will be applied in order to determine the prevalence percentage: Prevalence (%) is calculated as Positive Samples / Total Observed x 100.

Results

Three hundred seventeen (n = 150) patients who tested positive for intestinal helminth infections were included in our study. Healthy people who tested negative for intestinal helminth infections and who visited hospitals but did not exhibit any signs of an intestinal helminth infection are included in the comparative control group.

Stool Test Results

Figure 5 (A) : Stool color related percentage of Intestinal helminths patients.

B
I

Black color was found the highest color (39.61%) of stool of infected patients.

Figure 5 (B): Stool consistency percentage of Intestinal helminths patients.

L

Loose Stool consistency was recorded highest percentage (57.14%) of infected patients.

Figure. .5 (C) Gender specific prevalence of Intestinal helminths disease in children

The highest prevalence of cyst no. (61.54%) found in female, *E. vermicularis* (48.72%) found in female, *A. duodenale* (51.28%) found in female, *H. nana* (33.33%) found in female, *T. trichura* (23.08%) found in male, *F. buski* (27.69%) found in male, *ghomin* (20.51%) found in male.

Figure 5 (D). Gender specific prevalence of sign and symptoms of Intestinal helminths disease in children.

Figure 5 (E) : Age related prevalence of Intestinal helminths disease in children

The highest prevalence of cyst no. (61.54%) found at age group <13 years, *E. vermicularis* (48.72%) at age group 5-6 years, *A. duodenale* (51.28%) at age group 5-6 years, *H. nana* (33.33%) at age group 5-6 years, *T. trichura* (23.08%) at age group <13 years, *F. buski* (27.69%) at age group <13 years, *ghomin* (20.51%) at age group 5-6 years.

The highest prevalence of sign and symptoms vomiting and abdominal pain (87.18%) found at age group 5-6 years and weight loss (86%) found at age group <5.

Figure 5 (F): Age related prevalence of sign and symptoms of Intestinal helminths disease in children

Figure 5 (G). Simple line of Area by pH of stool of intestinal helminths infected patients.

The highest pH was recorded 7.1 in jarma and lowest pH was 5.5 in Behzadi chikarkot, district Kohat.

Figure 5 (H) : Prevalence of Intestinal helminths ova in stool sample

The highest ova percentage of giardia (19.48%) were found in infected patient's stool sample.

Results of Hematological and Biochemical Analysis

Table 1 (A). Overall Comparative Analysis of Hematological and Biochemical parameters of Intestinal helminths infected patients and non-infected individuals

Blood parameters	Infected patients	Non-infected
Albumin to globulin ratio	1.27±0.7	2.6 ± 0.29
TLC (cell/μL)	10.94±3.91×10 ³ / μL	10.26±7.09×10 ³ / μL
RBC (cell/μL)	4.49±0.56×10 ⁶ / μL	4.9 ± 1.24 × 10 ⁶ / μL
HB (g/dL)	11.64±1.23 g/dL	12.73±2.31 g/dL
HCT (%)	42.16±2.44 %	30.7 ± 9.3%
MCV (fL)	75.4±3.34 fL	81.77±8.49 fL
MCH (pg/cell)	36.21±2.83 pg	27.25 ± 7.1 pg
MCHC (g/dL)	35.03±3.61 g/dL	33.29 ± 3.4 g/dL
PLT (cell/μL)	291.07±48.7×10 ³ / μL	249.21±107.89×10 ³ / μL
Neutrophils (cell/μL)	57.56±8.43 ×10 ³ / μL	70.58±15.22×10 ³ / μL
Lymphocytes (cell/μL)	31.53±9.22×10 ³ / μL	20.75±12.95×10 ³ / μL
Monocytes (cell/μL)	7.31±3.87×10 ³ / μL	6.83±3.08×10 ³ / μL
Eosinophils (cell/μL)	5.09±1.23×10 ³ / μL	1.50±2.034×10 ³ / μL

In current study, an analysis of the hematological and biochemical parameters was performed in patients with and without intestinal helminths infection. Results of complete blood count (CBC) of 150 confirmed intestinal helminths infection were randomly choosing and compared with CBC reports of non-infected individuals. mean values of intestinal helminths infection, Albumin to globulin ratio (1.27±0.7), Red Blood Cell (RBC) (4.49±0.56×10⁶/μL), Hemoglobin (HB) (11.64±1.23 g/dL), Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (75.4±3.34 fL) and Neutrophils (57.56±8.43×10³/ μL) were less than median values of normal. Mean values for Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) of both patients and control was almost same and Hematocrit (HCT) (42.16±2.44%), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH) (75.4±3.34 pg), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (35.03±3.61 g/dL), Platelets (PLT) (291.07±48.7×10³/ μL), Lymphocytes (31.53±9.22×10³/ μL), Monocytes (7.31±3.87×10³/ μL) and Eosinophils (5.09±1.23×10³/ μL) was higher than normal median values in Table 4.1(A).

Table 1 (B). Age - wise Comparative Analysis of Hematological and Biochemical parameters of Intestinal helminths infected patients and non-infected individuals.

Age	<5 Years	5 to 8 Years	< 13 Years	Overall	P values	95% Conf Interval	
						Lower	Upper
Serum albumin to globulin ratio	1.46±0.74	1.31±0.63	1.09±0.65	1.27±0.7	0.001	1.1451	1.3698
TLC (cell/μL)	12.64±4.6×10 ³ / μL	11.57±3.58 ×10 ³ / μL	9.22±2.64 ×10 ³ / μL	10.94±3.91 ×10 ³ / μL	0.001	10.318	11.564
RBC (cell/μL)	4.54±0.490.56×10 ⁶ / μL	4.16±0.6×10 ⁶ / μL	4.67±0.48 ×10 ⁶ / μL	4.49±0.56 ×10 ⁶ / μL	0.001	4.4039	4.5818
HB (g/dL)	11.58±0.741.23 g/dL	12.13±1.37 g/dL	11.39±1.35 g/dL	11.64±1.23 g/dL	0.001	11.449	11.841

HCT (%)	41.97±2.04± 2.44 %	42.14±2.69 %	42.31±2.57%	42.16±2.44%	0.001	41.768	42.546
MCV (fL)	75.48±3.05 ±3.34 fL	77.26±2.95 fL	74.16±3.25 fL	75.4±3.34 fL	0.002	74.864	75.929
MCH (g/cell)	36.04±3.7± 2.83 pg	35.67±2.83 pg	36.68±1.75 pg	36.21±2.83 pg	0.003	35.76	36.662
MCHC (g/dL)	34.7±3.62± 3.61 g/dL	34.83±3.77 g/dL	35.41±3.45 g/dL	35.03±3.61 g/dL	0.005	34.452	35.6
PLT (cell/μL)	305.54±36.5 4±48.7×10 ³ / μL	256.58±40. 41×10 ³ / μL	301.33±51.35 ×10 ³ / μL	291.07±48.7× 10 ³ / μL	0.001	283.32	298.82
Neutrophils (cell/μL)	56.6±4.79± 8.43 ×10 ³ / μL	57.08±8.78 ×10 ³ / μL	58.63±10.17× 10 ³ / μL	57.56±8.43× 10 ³ / μL	0.034	56.222	58.908
Lymphocytes (cell/μL)	33.4±4.79± 9.22×10 ³ / μL	31.38±9.98 ×10 ³ / μL	30.16±10.97× 10 ³ / μL	31.53±9.22× 10 ³ / μL	0.001	30.058	32.994
Monocytes (cell/μL)	5.68±0.96± 3.87×10 ³ / μL	7.95±4.04× 10 ³ / μL	8.19±4.68×10 ³ / μL	7.31±3.87×10 ³ / μL	0.04	6.6959	7.9275
Eosinophils (cell/μL)	4.32±0.96±1 .23×10 ³ / μL	5.35±1.14× 10 ³ / μL	5.53±1.19×10 ³ / μL	5.09±1.23×10 ³ / μL	0.001	4.8954	5.2864

In current study, age-wise comparison showed significant difference (p 0.005) that the Albumin to globulin ratio (1.46±0.74), TLC (12.64±4.6), PLT (305.54±36.54) and Lymphocytes (33.4±4.79) values were highest in less than 5 years old patients and HB (12.13±1.37) and MCV (77.26±2.95) were found highest in the age between the 5 to 8 years while the value of RBC (4.67±0.48), HCT (42.31±2.57), MCH (36.68±1.75), MCHC (35.41±3.45), Neutrophils (58.63±10.17), Monocytes (8.19±4.68) and Eosinophils (5.53±1.19) were highest in the age less than 13 year patients in Table 4.2 (B).

Table 1 (C). Gender-wise Comparative Analysis of Hematological and Biochemical parameters of Intestinal helminths infected patients and non-infected individuals

Age	Gender	MN/SD	Non-infected CBC	P Value	95% Conf Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Albumin to globulin ratio	Male	1.21±0.06	2.6 ± 0.29	0.0003	1.1506	1.3494
	Female	1.29±0.04				
TLC (cell/μL)	Male	10.73±0.54 × 10 ³ / μL	10.26±7.09× 10 ³ / μL	0.0001	10.441	11.409
	Female	11.12±0.38× 10 ³ / μL				
RBC (cell/μL)	Male	4.45±0.22× 10 ⁶ / μL	4.9 ± 1.24 × 10 ⁶ / μL	0.0001	4.3906	4.5894
	Female	4.53±0.15 × 10 ⁶ / μL				
HB (g/dL)	Male	11.63±0.58 g/dL	12.73±2.31 g/dL	0.0001	11.608	11.682

	Female	11.66±0.40 g/dL				
HCT (%)	Male	42.30±2.12%	30.7 ± 9.3%	0.0001	41.830	42.500
	Female	42.03±1.43%				
MCV (fL)	Male	76.01±3.80 fL	81.77±8.49 fL	0.0001	74.024	76.856
	Female	74.87±2.55 fL				
MCH (g/dL)	Male	35.65±1.78	27.25 ± 7.1 pg	0.0001	34.878	37.462
	Female	36.69±1.25				
MCHC (g/dL)	Male	34.94±1.75	33.29 ± 3.4 g/dL	0.0001	34.821	35.219
	Female	35.10±1.19				
PLT (cell/ μ L)	Male	287.27±14.36× 10 ³ / μ L	249.21±107.89 × 10 ³ / μ L	0.0001	282.03	299.57
	Female	294.33±10.01 × 10 ³ / μ L				
Neutrophils (cell/ μ L)	Male	58.80±2.94× 10 ³ / μ L	70.58±15.22× 10 ³ / μ L	0.0001	54.811	60.499
	Female	56.51±1.92× 10 ³ / μ L				
Lymphocytes (cell/ μ L)	Male	29.93±1.50× 10 ³ / μ L	20.75±12.95 × 10 ³ / μ L	0.0001	27.733	35.087
	Female	32.89±1.12× 10 ³ / μ L				
Monocytes (cell/ μ L)	Male	7.31±0.37× 10 ³ / μ L	6.83±3.08 × 10 ³ / μ L	0.007	6.5233	8.1212
	Female	7.31±0.25× 10 ³ / μ L				
Eosinophils (cell/ μ L)	Male	5.23±0.26× 10 ³ / μ L	1.50±2.034	0.0002	4.7945	5.4155
	Female	4.98±0.17× 10 ³ / μ L				

The results also showed significant differences (p 0.007) in some hematological parameters. Gender-wise comparative analysis results showed that the male patients' MCV (76.01±3.80), Neutrophils (58.80±2.94) and Eosinophils (5.23±0.26) were higher than females patients while Albumin to globulin ratio (1.21±0.06), TLC (10.73±0.54), RBC (4.45±0.22), MCH (35.65±1.78), MCHC (34.94±1.75), PLT (287.27±14.36), Lymphocytes (29.93±1.50) and Eosinophils (5.23±0.26) were less than females patients. And HB (11.63±0.58), HCT (42.30±2.12) and Monocytes (7.31±0.37) of both patients were almost same in Table 4.2 (C).

Discussion

In underdeveloped nations, intestinal parasite infections are a serious health concern, especially in tropical and subtropical regions. An estimated 3.7 billion people are impacted each year; children, especially those in Pakistan and Kohat, account for

the majority of cases (Awaad et al., 2023). The children's susceptibility to frequent intestinal illnesses may have been significantly influenced by poverty and illiteracy. Mothers' educational attainment and work position possess a substantial

impact on the prevalence of intestinal parasite infections (LU & ES, 2008).

According to this study, intestinal parasites continue to affect a significant number of our rural children in the Kohat district. Most affected were children. For both genders, the age group below 13 years old had the highest prevalence of cyst no. (61.54%) when compared to the other age groups. Children in this age group were probably most exposed to infections, particularly while they were playing in hazardous areas. Our incidence rate is comparable to a previously published finding from a study of schoolchildren in the rural area of Mardan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, which found that the prevalence of STH among study participants was 20 (6.65%), 10 (3.33%) of those aged 4–7, 8 (2.66%) of those aged 7–10, and 2 (0.66%) of those aged 10–13. *Ascaris lumbricoides* accounted for 60% of all worm infections, followed by *Trichuris trichiura* (35%), and mixed infections (5%). Underweight eating habits and the presence of STH infection were found to be significantly correlated (Ullah *et al.*, 2023).

Our study showed that the highest prevalence of cyst no. (61.54%), *E. vermicularis* (48.72%), *A. duodenale* (51.28%), *H. nana* (33.33%) found in female higher than male children, *T. trichura* (23.08%), *F. buski* (27.69%), *ghomin* (20.51%) found in male children in highest. Our also showed that the highest prevalence of cyst no. (61.54%) found at age group <13 years, *E. vermicularis* (48.72%) at age group 5-6 years, *A. duodenale* (51.28%) at age group 5-6 years, *H. nana* (33.33%) at age group 5-6 years, *T. trichura* (23.08%) at age group <13 years, *F. buski* (27.69%) at age group <13 years, *ghomin* (20.51%) at age group 5-6 years

Because of the unequal protein distribution between globulin and albumin sections, it is well known that inflammation and infection lower serum albumin levels (Chen *et al.*, 2014). This is thought to be the reason of the reduced albumin levels in the participant groups with intestinal helminth infections and/or inflammation in the current investigation. According to the current study, the age group between 7 and 13 years old had the lowest albumin to globulin ratio (1.09±0.65). Similar to what Mkhize *et al.* (2018) reported, our investigation found that people with normal CRP had

significantly lower albumin levels in unadjusted BMI [RRR = 0.8, p = 0.001], normal weight [RRR = 0.7, p = 0.003], and overweight [RRR = 0.5, p = 0.001]. Prealbumin was considerably greater in people with uncorrected BMI [RRR = 1.2, p = 0.034] and overweight [RRR = 1.4, p = 0.052] and albumin was significantly lower in people with elevated CRP [RRR = 0.8, p = 0.050].

Some blood test results in our intestinal helminth infection CBC report indicated significant variations (p 0.007). Results of a gender-wise comparative analysis revealed that while some blood parameters, such as TLC (10.73±0.54), RBC (4.45±0.22), MCH (35.65±1.78), MCHC (34.94±1.75), PLT (287.27±14.36), lymphocytes (29.93±1.50), and eosinophils (5.23±0.26), were lower in male patients than in female patients, male patients had higher MCV (76.01±3.80), neutrophils (58.80±2.94), and eosinophils (5.23±0.26). The current study demonstrated that leucocytosis, primarily eosinophilia, was more common in infected individuals than in non-infected ones. This was in line with findings that indicated infected cases had a higher number of W.B.Cs (10.6) x 10³ cells/mm³ compared to the control group (6.31) x 10³ cells/mm³ (74.7%). The ability of eosinophils to bind to parasites' walls and release granules that cause their demise could be the cause of this (Bayoumy *et al.*, 2018).

Conclusions And Recommendations

The current study revealed that the Children infected with Helminths parasites having weight loss followed by abdominal pain and vomiting. The stool consistency was mostly loose and black and brown in colour of the infected children. The cyst no and *Enterobius vermicularis* were found more prevalent in the stool samples of the children. The Hb and RBC level were found insufficient as compare to the control. The female children were more infected as compare to male.

The helminths parasites were found equally in all areas of district Kohat

Implement community-wide deworming initiatives to reduce the prevalence of *Enterobius vermicularis* and *Ancylostoma duodenale* among children, with a focus on high-risk groups. Educate parents, caregivers, and schools about the importance of personal

hygiene practices, such as regular handwashing, wearing footwear, and maintaining clean living environments, to prevent helminth infections. Address weight loss and anemia in infected children by providing access to balanced diets rich in nutrients, particularly iron, to improve Hb and RBC levels. Develop strategies targeting female children, who showed higher infection rates, to ensure equitable access to healthcare, education, and resources for preventing and managing infections. Strengthen sanitation infrastructure in district Kohat, including safe drinking water, proper waste disposal, and access to clean toilets, to curb the transmission of helminths.

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